

IMPACT RESISTANCE OF 3-D GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A 2-D laminate, a stitched laminate, a 3-D orthogonal and an angle-interlock were tested under high velocity impact with a gelatine projectile to investigate the contribution of the various through-the-thickness reinforcements. A damage study showed that the stitched laminate and the 3-D orthogonal provided a significant improvement in damage resistance without sacrificing the in-plane properties whereas the yarn undulations of the interlock produced a loss of mechanical properties and a poor impact strength. The finite element code PLEXUS was used to predict fiber breakage in the interlock, which was in a good agreement with the experimental observations.

INTRODUCTION

For the past ten years, there has been an increasing need for composites with better resistance and tolerance to delamination, often considered as a weak point when subjected to impact loading. This has been met by the use of tougher matrices, interleaves or out-of-plane reinforcement. The latter solution may be achieved by various ways: stitched laminates which combine the lay-up technique and a final stitching, multi-dimensional architectures which include various directions of fiber reinforcement such as 3-D orthogonal, braiding, knitting and some architectures woven such that the warp yarns contribute to the out-of-plane reinforcement by the interlacing of the different layers, such as the angle-interlock [1]. The fibrous preform is then impregnated or injected via the RTM process. Most of the experimental studies have focused on the measurement of the high fracture toughness, G_{IC} and G_{IIC} , of stitched and 3-D orthogonal composites [2,3], however little has been published about the impact behavior of stitched laminates and angle-interlocks [4,5,6]. For low velocity impacts carried out on 3-D and 5-D orthogonal composites, per Charpy and per falling weight methods, Shen Chou [4] found that braided composites showed an improved impact strength and gradual deformation until failure; the energy required for damage initiation and the energy absorbed were both found higher, when compared to the 2-D laminates. At higher velocity (up to 86m/s) with a hard impactor, Gong [5] found that damage in braided composites occurred at a threshold similar to that of laminates but that it was more confined. That retarded damage propagation but led to fiber tow breakage. In the same range of velocity (up to 100m/s), Dexter [6] showed that stitched quasi-isotropic laminates impacted by a hard impactor exhibited lower damage areas and better residual strain-to-failure in compression-after-impact tests than unstitched laminates.

The scope of the present study is to describe the contribution of the various through-the-thickness reinforcements such as the stitch and the undulation of the interlock on their impact behavior, when impacted at high velocity (130-300m/s) by a soft projectile. First, for this purpose, the damage threshold, extent and distribution in impacted plates were studied using ultrasonic inspection and microscopy. Second, the strain at various locations was recorded during the impact. That information was used to validate the finite element code PLEXUS where the projectile is modeled by a fluid and subsequently to obtain the full strain field. The damage observations, the strain field and the mechanical properties including in-plane properties, interlaminar strength and strain energy release rate, when available, were used to relate the specificity of each architecture to the damage extent and modes.

MATERIAL

The choice of the four types of architectures that were tested was such that the same fiber volume fraction, same tow size, same resin and the same directions of main reinforcement (fill and warp) were kept. This led to a bending stiffness of the interlock architecture different from the other ones. All the architectures were woven with carbon fibers of the class T300, 6k. Eight plies of five harness satin woven fabric were used for the 2-D reference and the stitched laminate. The stitching was performed with T900 (Torayca) carbon fibers with a square step of 5 mm. A sketch of the interlock showing the periodic structure in the fill and warp directions is shown on Fig. 1. The architectures were then injected with the resin RTM6 from Ciba-Geigy, and cured according to the manufacturer's cure cycle. All the plates were inspected by C-scan to ensure that they were porosity and defect free. The fiber volume content of the plates was then measured following ASTM D3171 using a density of 1.145 g/cm³ for RTM6 (Table 1).

Table 1. Porosity and fiber volume content for the four architectures

Architecture	Porosity (%)	Fiber volume content
2-D Fabric	0.9	58.0
Stitched	-	54.6
Interlock	-	53.8
3-D	1.6	55.6

The geometric characteristics of the interlock obtained after the RTM process were different from the ideal ones sketched on Fig. 1. The fiber undulation involved the presence of segments either off-axis or aligned with the warp direction. The angle of the yarns pertaining to the *off-axis* segments was around 25° whereas the fill yarns were straight [7].

EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

All the static properties were obtained at a cross-head rate of 1 mm per minute on an Instron testing machine. For the impact tests, a gas gun was used to achieve velocities in the range 130-300m/s. The soft projectile made of gelatine had its density, mass and temperature kept constant and was shot perpendicular to the target. The projectile was protected by a sabot during the acceleration phase in the gun and was prevented to impact the plate thanks to a stopping device. The velocity was measured by optical barriers after the sabot was arrested and just prior to the impact. The target consisted of a 250x250 mm plate clamped on a 200 mm diameter steel frame. A high speed camera was used to check that the projectile was not broken before impacting the center of the target. Each plate was instrumented with up to 14 strain gages that were connected to a Nicolet dynamic data acquisition system. After each shot, the surface damage was

investigated by visual inspection and the internal damage by ultrasonic C-scan and microscopy on polished cross sections.

RESULTS

The in-plane static properties of the various materials are given in Table 2 and 3. E_{11} , ν_{12} , G_{12} refer to the in-plane elastic constants where the indices 1 and 2 denote the warp and fill directions respectively. ϵ_{11} , XT_{11} , XC_{11} and ILSS refer to the failure characteristics: strain-to-failure and strength in tension, normalized strength in compression and normalized interlaminar shear strength, respectively. Some of the values were taken from [7].

Table 2. Elastic constants for the four architectures -

lay-up	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)
2-D Fabric	65.5 ± 2.3	$65. \pm 0.9$	0.028 ± 0.011	4.8 ± 0.1
Stitched	62.2 ± 3.5	-	0.064 ± 0.03	5.0 ± 0.1
Interlock	42.6 ± 0.6	58.7 ± 0.4	0.046 ± 0.011	4.6 ± 0.1
3-D	57.5 ± 1.8	57.1 ± 1.1	0.028 ± 0.008	4.1 ± 0.1

Table 3. Failure characteristics for the four architectures

lay-up	XT_{11} (MPa)	ϵ_{11} (%)	XC_{11} (-)	ILSS (-)
2-D Fabric	776 ± 28	1.2 ± 0.1	100%	100%
Stitched	657 ± 38	1.2 ± 0.0	87%	110%
Interlock	334 ± 7	1.3 ± 0.1	46%	112%
3-D	780 ± 50	1.2 ± 0.1	97%	90%

The fracture toughness of the stiched laminate in mode I was measured using DCB coupons and was found to be more than five times that of the 2-D reference. In mode II, using ENF coupons, the fracture toughness corresponding to a propagation of 10mm was measured to be more than twice that of the 2-D reference. These two parameters were not determined for the 3-D and interlock architectures.

High velocity impacts with a gelatine projectile were performed on plates for the four types of composites. The damage threshold, determined by the C-scan inspection, was similar for the 2-D, the stitched laminate and the 3-D architecture and slightly higher than that of the interlock architecture. The impact induced damage, as the velocity was increased, can be described as following (Table 4). All the architectures showed resin damage as their first damage mode, in term of matrix cracking in the resin rich areas for the interlock architecture or in term of delamination and transverse matrix cracking for the three other ones. Some of the matrix cracks were oriented at 45° with respect to the impact direction, similar to what is often observed for low velocity impacts. The delamination was often located at the mid-plane or between the mid-plane and the back surface, however, which differs from the delamination through the thickness in a cone-shaped zone often observed at low velocity.

At higher velocities, some bundles on the front surface of the 2-D, stitched and 3-D were observed to debond and to be subsequently scraped off the surface. The higher the velocity, the bigger the delamination, until a velocity of around 275 m/s where internal fiber breakage was observed in the 2-D and the stitched laminate. For the same range of velocity, no fiber breakage was observed in the 3-D composites. The interlock showed fiber breakage of the warp bundles at a velocity as low as 190 m/s, which produced a macroscopic crack through the thickness and perforation at higher velocities.

Table 4. Impact damage modes of the various architectures

	2D reference	Stitched 5mm	3D	Interlock
first damage	v ~ 150 m/s delamination and matrix cracking	v ~ 150 m/s delamination and matrix cracking	v ~ 150 m/s delamination and matrix cracking	v ~ 140 m/s matrix cracking
front surface damage (matrix cracking))	v ~ 160 m/s	v ~ 210 m/s	v ~ 200 m/s	-
front surface damage (yarns scraped off)	v ~ 225 m/s	v ~ 210 m/s	v ~ 240 m/s	-
back surface damage (matrix cracking)	v ~ 275 m/s	v ~ 210 m/s	v ~ 190 m/s	v ~ 190 m/s
fiber breakage	v ~ 275 m/s	v ~ 275 m/s	-	v ~ 190 m/s

Since it has been shown that the damage of the 2-D, stitched and 3D composites consists of delamination in the range 150-273m/s, it is possible to compare their respective damage extents. It is shown on Fig. 2 that the damage area of the stitched and 3-D composites, as measured per C-scan is lower than that of the 2-D reference by a factor of around 35%. The pattern of the damage zone was symmetric with respect to the warp and fill directions which is attributed to the similar material properties in these two directions. It is not relevant to compare the damage area of the interlock with the others since fiber breakage already occurred at 190 m/s. Above that velocity, the damage zone was elongated in the fill direction, forming a narrow zone around the macroscopic crack previously described.

A comparison at 140m/s, below damage threshold, of the curves strain versus time for the gages located along the fill and warp axes, 25mm away from the plate center, shows very similar features both in amplitude and time wise for the 2-D and stitched composites. The same curves for the interlock architecture show a similar shape but with a higher amplitude (Fig. 3) which may be attributed to a lower elastic modulus in the warp direction (Table 2). For a given architecture, the higher the impact velocity, the larger the amplitude and frequency of the signals. Depending of the impact damage induced in the plate, delamination or fiber breakage, the shape of the curves gets altered because of load redistribution. In the case of the interlock architecture, the gage located along the fibers in the warp direction at 25mm away from the center showed that the fibers were subjected to higher strains than in the other architectures, up to 1.2%, which is higher than the strain level at which fiber breakage occur in static tension (Fig. 4). That is in agreement with the fiber breakage observed on the interlock plate impacted at 190m/s. At that velocity, the 2-D, stitched and 3-D composites underwent delamination and the level of strain seen by the same gage remained below 1% which was consistent with the absence of broken fiber on the plate.

DISCUSSION

From Table 1, it can be inferred that the in-plane properties of the 3-D and stitched composites were not significantly lower than that of the 2-D reference whereas a sharp loss for the tensile and compressive properties of the interlock along the warp direction was observed. This has been explained in [7] by the fiber undulation present in the warp direction.

From Figure 1 and the observation of the damage modes summarized in Table 4, it is shown that the through-the-thickness reinforcement of the 3-D and stitched laminates do not prevent delamination to occur but significantly reduce its extent. The stitches through the thickness slightly reduce the surface of the interface planes but continuous potential planes of delamination between the fill and the warp directions still exist. Once a delamination is created in the plate, it

is subjected to both mode I and II loading during the impact. The role of the stitch consists in preventing the plies to open in mode I or to slide in mode II as much as in the 2-D unstitched laminates which is reflected by the larger fracture toughness in mode I and II of the stitched laminate. No relation with the value of the shear strength was found. The stitches also lead to more matrix cracking in their vicinity. Moreover, the reinforcement through the thickness, even at high velocity, was not cut by the extending delamination keeping the integrity of the composite.

The behavior of the interlock architecture was totally different in the sense that delamination was prevented by the absence of potential delamination planes; only a few local debonds were observed and confined to a zone much smaller than in the three other architectures. Most of the impact energy seemed to be dissipated into fiber breakage leading to perforation at higher velocities.

The finite element code PLEXUS, using an arbitrary lagrangian-eulerian approach, was validated by the comparison of the experimental and calculated strain curves on plates impacted at low velocity that had no or little damage. It was then used to predict fiber breakage in the interlock architecture, using a maximum strain criterion in the direction of the fibers. It can be seen on Fig. 5 that the maximum strain calculated in the warp direction for a shot at 190m/s is above the strain capacity of the material which is therefore predicted to fail by fiber breakage. This is in good agreement with the experimental observations. The shape of the zone where the criterion was reached was elongated along the fill direction and did correspond to the location of the crack through the thickness that was observed on the plate. A lower modulus along the warp direction gave rise to larger strain levels in the warp direction leading to premature failure because of the relatively low strength in that direction.

CONCLUSION

Plates consisting of a 2-D laminate, a stitched laminate, a 3-D orthogonal composite and an interlock architecture were impacted at high velocity (130-300m/s) by a gelatine projectile. The damage threshold, determined by the C-scan inspection, was similar for the 2-D, the stitched laminate and the 3-D architecture and slightly higher than that of the interlock architecture.

It was found that the reinforcement through the thickness of the 3-D orthogonal and the stitched laminate provided a reduction of 35% of the delamination area compared to the 2-D reference. That reinforcement was not cut by the extending delamination and proved to be an efficient crack stopper keeping the integrity of the composite after high velocity impact. This could be of importance in the case of the presence of free edges in a structure. This improvement in damage resistance was achieved without any significant loss of the in-plane properties.

The geometry of the angle-interlock architecture chosen in this study was such that the undulation of the warp yarns that interlaced adjacent layers suppressed the existence of potential planes of delamination but entailed a sharp loss of mechanical properties in the warp direction. That resulted in a confined damage zone and in a velocity at which fiber breakage occurred much lower than that of the other architectures.

The finite element code PLEXUS, modeling the gelatine projectile as a fluid, was used to predict fiber breakage in the interlock architecture, using a maximum strain criterion in the direction of the fibers. It was in good agreement with the experimental observations, as far as the velocity at which failure occurred and the shape of the damage zone. A lower modulus gave rise to larger strain levels in the warp direction leading to premature failure because of a low strength in that direction.

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Thickness

Warp direction

Figure 1. Geometry of the interlock architecture

Figure 2. Damage area after impact for the various architectures

Figure 3. Comparison of the curves strain versus time for the 2-D and interlock at 140m/s

(2-D)

Figure 4. Comparison of the deformation during the impact for the 2-D and interlock architectures at higher velocity (225m/s and 235m/s respectively) -

Figure 5. Maximum strain distribution for the interlock (190m/s)